

**THE USE OF LOCAL INFORMATION IN THE LESSONS OF A PERSON
AND HIS HEALTH (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE 8TH GRADE)**

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Abstract: Education in secondary schools, it is extremely important to conduct classes using local materials in increasing the effectiveness of the educational and educational process. What are local materials?

Keywords: local material, provide information, specific plant, biological characteristics.

First of all, local material is to provide information about objects that are not included in textbooks of educational subjects. Without deviating from the description of the laws under study in this case, the examples that are given to them are the interpretation of the use of local materials.

Secondly, to relate to the topic on which evidence of specific plant, animal species and their biological characteristics is being read for different regions of the Republic. Because, in the large natural and geographical regions of Uzbekistan, sandy deserts, Fergana and Zarafshan valleys, southern city's with a subtropical climate, specific species of some derived families and categories have spread. Textbooks do not have the opportunity to dwell on each of them separately.

Even in the lessons of a person and his health (Grade 8), local materials can be used to some extent when passing each topic. When passing topics related to the anatomical structure of the human body (bones, muscles, structure and diseases of the internal organs), it is necessary to use the ideas outlined in the works of the Great Ibn Sina in this area. Despite the fact that the study of the human organism was practiced in the IX-X centuries, scientists (including Ibn Sina) had an

understanding of the structure of human organs.

A special aspect of the work of the laws of Ibn Sina —Tib is devoted to the coverage of this issue. In addition to the information described in the textbook, they can be used as local material. It should be explained that 1000 years ago it was said that infectious diseases are spread by Invisible animals-microbes, and for the Prevention of diseases it is necessary to observe the rules of protection of the external environment, personal and social hygiene.

In the lessons on the physiological topic, it is necessary to dwell more on the specific effects of hot climatic conditions on water, salt and precipitation, and describe the work of Uzbek scientists in this area. Academician yo, a world-famous Uzbek scientist who recommended the Causes, Consequences and ways of treating thyroid dysfunction, one of the most dangerous diseases. About the contribution of Kh.Turakulov to the world medical science is spoken.

The use of local information primarily depends on the teacher's erudition, searchability and dedication of his work. Otherwise, he will not be able to convey the content of the textbook topics either.

Historical local materials can be used as follows when a word is swallowed up about the work of Central Asian medical scientists who lived in the IX-XI centuries:

At first, the socio-economic and natural-scientific environment in Central Asia will be discussed in the IX-XI centuries. Later, information is told about the work of Ibn Sina, who was considered the allomites of this period.

Readers are shown a portrait and some of Abu Ali Ibn Sina's works and informed of their life and work.

Abu Ali Ibn Sina (980-1037) was erected in the village of Afshona near Bukhara. Like Beruni, he was aware of many areas of natural science, but perfectly knew the science of Medicine at the level of that time. His masterpiece called the laws of-Tib has been taught as a textbook in European medical educational institutions for

centuries. The first book deals with the structure of the human body and the origin and symptoms of diseases. The second book deals with simple drugs and their effects on the human body (80). Treatment of diseases in the third book. In the fourth book, surgery, and in the fifth book, information is given about complex drugs, poisons and substances used against them. The ring, which was quite common at that time, believes that the causes of cholera, measles, tuberculosis are small animals that are not visible to the eye. Like all animals, plants also claim that they feed, grow and reproduce. In his opinion, plants stand in the lower, animals in the middle, and man in the upper stage of their development. Ibn Sina-other than the laws of Tib, had as many as 150 works, such as the book of healing, the book of knowledge. In Europe, it was known as Avisenna, the famous K.Linnaeus named in his honor a constellation of systemgulmates (avisennia), named the net of the rough canopy - Avisenna rough canopy from the gulhayridoshs. Ibn Sina recognizes God, but believes that his power is limited. Tries to put a limit between science and religion. He dies in hamadan, Iran, in 1160.

At the end of the lesson, the teacher concluded that during the period when natural science in Europe was in crisis, in Central Asia he developed a stroke, in which he once again emphasizes the merits of Ibn Sina.

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